

Policy Implementation of the Prostitution Prevention in Surabaya City

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Abstract

The implementation of the Prostitution Prevention and Control Policy in Surabaya, East Java Province has been implemented but there were still various obstacles, among others, based on policy implementation. Children will lose the right to enjoy education and welfare, many elements of society reject the plan to close Dolly's localization. Besides the difficulties in terms of the thousands of sex workers who need to be rehabilitated by being given job training and repatriated to them they will need a very large compensation fund. Based on public policy instruments it is known that from the voluntary model instrument, commercial sex workers (CSWs) have been given skills training as well as spiritual spray or recitation regularly to be repatriated, based on mixed instruments, closing localization begins with socialization involving all levels of Surabaya City Government, the entire community in Dolly, local neighbourhood or halmet, community leaders, religious leaders, and officials. Then the warning board was installed, but the installation of the bulletin board at the end of Jarak street or near DukuhKupang which got resistance. Dolly Residents and Jarak held a bulletin board after hundreds of residents burned tires in the middle of the road as a refusal. Residents also attacked the police with stones. Other problems regarding compensation, many pimps who are also halmets who enter the names of other people either from CSWs or not in the CSW data collection will be submitted to be requested for compensation funds to the City Government in the hope that the compensation funds will be disbursed and will be shared between pimps and Outside sex workers or ordinary women. Based on mandatory instruments, the Surabaya City Government to prevent and control prostitution in Dolly Jarak provides facilities for ex-pimps, future hopeful women (former CSWs) and affected communities. Based on the collaboration of actors in the implementation of policies on prevention and repetition of prostitution in Surabaya, it is known that local actors both in the form of formal institutions and informal institutions include: Surabaya City Government Actors, namely: Surabaya Mayor, Surabaya City Government Agency, Putat Jaya District Official ; Affected Communities: CSWs, pimps, street vendors, Neighbourhood (RT) or Hamlet (RW), NGOs; and the Indonesian National Police and National Army. Regional Actors include: East Java Provincial Government: East Java Governor, who played a role in closing the localization of Dolly and National Actors in the form of the Ministry of Social Affairs, knowing that Dolly's prostitution closure was initiated by the Ministry of Social Affairs and then followed by the Mayor of Surabaya. The Surabaya City Government is actually only as the executor of the policies that have been made by the Central Government and forwarded by the Regional Government.

Keywords: Implementation, Prostitution Prevention and Control Policy

INTRODUCTION

Human trafficking has developed into a concerning humanitarian issue. One form of human trafficking is human trafficking for the purpose of sexual exploitation. Victims of these crimes often occur among women who are trafficked for the purpose of sexual exploitation who often experience sexual crimes. Sexual crimes against women are a form of torture for men to carry out activities with the aim of sexual gratification (MikhaRoslinaAmbarita 2014). Various forms of sexual crimes against children include sexual violence, sexual offenses, sexual harassment, the act of subjecting someone to unwanted or unjustified sexual acts, robbery, rape, and abuse (Ronald B. Flowers, 2006: 103). Furthermore, Ambarita (2014) stated that:

The phenomenon of human trafficking for the purpose of commercial sexual exploitation has long been developing in various countries in the world, including countries in the Southeast Asian region such as Thailand, Vietnam, Indonesia and Cambodia. Cambodia is a country of origin, transit and destination for men, women and children who are trafficked for the purposes of sexual exploitation and forced labor. Many women and children are trafficked to Vietnam, Thailand and Malaysia for sexual exploitation or as domestic workers, while men are trafficked as forced labor in agriculture and fishing.

The occurrence of sexual crimes against women raises various negative impacts on women who are victims of sexual crimes where they experience trauma and mental and physical disorders due to sexual exploitation and abuse. and certain body parts as service commodities and to obtain material through activities of a sexual nature. Indonesia is a country whose sex expenditure is quite high, reaching 2.25 billion US dollars per year, prostitution is carried out illegally because it is considered a moral crime. UNICEF estimates that 30 percent of female prostitutes in Indonesia are under the age of 18 and that their pimps are still teenagers. (PawestriDwnesia: 2016). The perpetrators of prostitution do not appear to be deterred by the negative impact they will experience and ignore the prevailing norms. But actually for prostitutes themselves, the prostitution profession is a complex problem because it is closely related to poverty, ignorance, limited employment opportunities, and low self-esteem in a person. CSWs really understand that the practice of prostitution is against the values, religious and cultural norms of society.

So women who are trapped in a life of prostitution are women who are not only poor in wealth to fulfill their needs for life and their families, more than that they are poor in knowledge, poor in education, poor in moral, religion and cultural order and this is the responsibility of the State to be able to alleviate it. They are from a downturn in life according to what is mandated by the Basic Law above. In addition, the national normative basis also comes from the Ministry of Social Affairs of the Central Government in the form of Law of the Republic of Indonesia number 21 concerning the Eradication of the Crime of Trafficking in Persons which functions as a legal umbrella and provides compensation funds to commercial sex workers or prostitutes in the process of closing Dolly's localization.

Whereas regionally the normative basis is the Governor of East Java Decree number: 188/617 / KPTS / 013/2010 concerning the Provincial Action Plan for the Eradication of the Crime of Trafficking in Persons (TPPO) and Child Sexual Exploitation (ESA), East Java Province 2010-2015, which functions as a legal umbrella and providing compensation for pimps in the process of closing Dolly's brothels. With the normative support of the Central Government and the Provincial Government, the Surabaya City Government has a strong legal basis to realize the implementation of policies to prevent and combat prostitution in Surabaya. Especially if you look at conditions in the field that many of the commercial sex workers or sex workers are found to be children, whom likes 18 years old. This research was conducted in Surabaya, with the consideration that Surabaya is the capital of East Java Province, which has become the largest metropolitan city in the province, and is the second largest city in Indonesia after Jabodetabek and is the center of business, trade, industry and education in the Indonesian region, eastern part. The city is located 789 km east of Jakarta, 426 km northwest of Denpasar Bali and is located on the north coast of Java Island facing the Madura Strait and the Java Sea. Surabaya has an area of about 333, 063 km² with a population of 2,813,847 people (2014), as a metropolitan area it is a cultural gateway with a population of around 10 million, served by Juanda international airport, Tanjung Perak port, and Ujung port, so that Surabaya is a place where people with all interests meet. This is one of the causes of the growing prostitution. Dolly or Dolly Alley is the name of a prostitution area located in the area of Jarak, Pasar Kembang, Surabaya City, East Java Province, Indonesia. In this localization area, comfort women are "displayed" in a glass-walled room similar to a window. Looking at the above conditions, the activity of prostitution in Dolly is very contrary to human dignity as an Indonesian nation that is full of culture and is very religious. Therefore, prostitution activity must be prevented and overcome.

The implementation of the Surabaya City Government's policy to be able to realize the closure of Dolly's localization is a very big challenge because many people are deeply rooted in the economy through prostitution activities, such as the high risk for decision makers and even triggering many social waves. The closure of Dolly, which has been operating since 1967, was not easy. There was fierce controversy and rejection from both prostitutes and pimps. The efforts made by the Surabaya City Government are also in the world spotlight. A number of foreign media also reported. Radio Australia's website today, June 19th 2014 featured an article entitled '*Sex workers protest shutdown of Surabaya's "Dolly" red-light district*', which tells of their opposition to those who make a living from prostitution over the closure of the red light area in Hero City.

After Dolly was closed at that time, the government as a policy maker and implementor was faced with the challenge of being able to overcome the existing prostitution problem, considering that the government's function in dealing with prostitution problems is carried out by the Surabaya Social Service, empirically, mostly on the basis of laws and local regulations, which are still implemented. It requires technical rules that more concretely reach problems in the field, let alone the proliferation of hidden prostitution in cafes, stalls, restaurants, massage parlors, karaoke places, hotels, beauty and fitness salons, even now growing in boarding houses. This has become a tough homework for the Surabaya Regional Government, but it cannot be denied that Surabaya's great achievement has succeeded in closing Dolly's localization as the largest prostitution place in Southeast Asia. This proves to be a form of the successful implementation of the Surabaya government policy in preventing and overcoming prostitution.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Public Policy Implementation Theory

Policy implementation according to Michael and Hupe, (2002: 2). In the simple terms, it is "*what happens between policy expectations and (perceived) policy results*", (what happens between policy expectations and (considered) policy results and has two characters "... a concern to explain what happens and a concern to affect what happens" (attention to explain what happens and attention to influence what happens). Public policy implementation studies have grown since Pressman and Wildavsky's case study in the City of Oakland, California, encountered difficulties implementing personnel training programs in the late 1960s. The publication of Press Men and Wildavsky's (1973) work "*Implementation: How Great Expectations in Washington Are Dashed in Oakland*", and the decade of the 1970s to 1980s has made the study of public policy implementation enter a golden era. So since then, policy implementation scholars have made many important inputs in understanding policy implementation and the broader policy process. At that time Van Meter and Van Horn (1975), Sabatier and Mazmanian (1979, 1983) also developed top-down implementation framework models.

The assumption of top-down policy implementation is that public policies are mostly carried out by the government for the people, where participation takes the form of mobilization. Sabatier (1985: 22) as one of the initiators of the top-down model states that the essence of a top-down approach is "*it starts with a policy decision by government (often central government) officials and then tasks*". (Starting with a policy decision by

government officials (often the central government) and then the duties. An important question for policy implementation scholars such as Mazmanian and Sabatier (1983: 2) has a lot to do with attention to process evaluation: "Could out come be different? Can we learn experience and avoid similar problems in designing future public programs?" (Can the results be different? Can we and can learn to experience and avoid similar problems in future public programs?)

The contribution of the top-down approach from Sebatier and Mazmanian (1979), which is the contribution of American scholars. Like most top-down perspectives, Sebatier and Mazmanian begin their analysis with policy decisions made by representatives of government, causal theory of legislation or political support.

Sabatier, Mazrnanian (1983: 67) states that implementation is:

"The carrying out of a basic policy decision, usually incorporated in a statute but which can also take the form of important executive orders or court decisions. Ideally, that decision identifies the problem (s) to be addressed, stipulates the objective (s) to be pursued, and, in a variety of ways, "structure" the implementation process. The Process in normally runs through a number of stages beginning with passage of the basic statute, followed by the policy outputs (decisions) of the implementing agencies, the compliance of target groups with those decisions, the actual impacts-both intended and unintended-of those outputs, the perceived impacts of agency decisions, and finally, important revisions (or attempted revisions) in the basic statute".

From this definition, it can be explained that: first, implementation will be influenced by the extent to which policies deviate from previous policies. In this case, incremental changes tend to have a more positive impact than drastic (rational) changes. Second, the implementation process will be influenced by the number of organizational changes required. There is an assumption that effective implementation will be possible if the implementing agency is not required to implement it.

2.2 Prostitution

Prostitution or prostitution is the sale of sexual services, such as oral sex or sexual relations, for money. A person who sells sexual services is called a prostitute, which is now often referred to as a commercial sex worker (CSW). In a broader sense, a person who sells his services for something that is considered worthless is also called prostituting himself, for example a highly talented musician who mostly plays commercial songs. In Indonesia, prostitutes are often referred to as harlots or sundels. This shows that the behavior of the harlot is very bad and despicable and become an enemy of society, they are often shaved if they are caught by the law enforcement officers, they are also evicted because they are considered to have violated the sanctity of religion and they are also brought to court for violating the law. The work of prostitution has been known in society for centuries. This is evidenced by the many scattered records about them from time immemorial. The risks presented by prostitution include community unrest and the spread of sexually transmitted diseases, such as AIDS, which are common risks of unprotected free sex such as condoms.

Prostitution or Commercial Sex Worker comes from the Latin pro-stauree, which means allowing oneself to commit adultery, commit sexual immorality, sexual immorality, and bullying. While prostitutes are prostitutes or harlots, also known as prostitutes or moll women (Kartono: 2005). Immoral deafness is an act that is uncivilized because of the breakdown of sexual relations in the form of surrendering to many men, for sexual gratification, receiving fees or money from their services. Immoral deafness can also be said to be an act that fails to conform to moral norms. From the description of the history of the development of prostitution above, then in the basic of prostitution has existed since the existence of human civilization and continues until the present day, prostitution activity is a biological need between men and women and even to fulfill economic needs, mental satisfaction needs and so on. Whatever the term prostitutes, commercial sex workers, balloons and so on, are basically sex acts that violate social and religious norms both to meet biological needs and to fulfill other needs.

According to wikipedia, prostitution is the sale of sexual services, such as oral sex or real sex, for money. A person who sells sexual services is called a prostitute, which is now often referred to as a commercial sex worker (CSW). Meanwhile, according to Ekanurmawaty (2010), a commercial sex worker is someone who sells his services to have sexual relations for money. Prostitute is a profession that sells services to satisfy the sexual needs of customers. Usually this service is in the form of renting out the body. In Indonesian society, prostitution is viewed negatively, and those who rent or sell their bodies are often viewed as community trash.

Terence H et al. (1999) in the commercial sex industry includes: street prostitution, brothel prostitution, massage parlors, escort services, calling services, strip clubs, phone sex, child and adult pornography, internet and video pornography, and prostitution in tourism. Kartono (2001) explains that:

Sex is a psychic energy that helps encourage people to act actively. Not only doing in the field of sex, namely engaging in sexual relations or intercourse, but also engaging in non-sexual activities, for example participating in encouraging achievement in the fields of art, religion, social, cultural, moral, economic and so on. As psychic energy, sex becomes a motivation or impetus to act or behave. Freud called sex libido sexualis (libido = lascivious, sexual lust drive).

Prostitution has always existed in all countries, from ancient history to the present and has always been a social problem, or has become an object of traditional law that must be stopped or at least minimized. Furthermore, Walter Reckless divides prostitutes into several groups as follows:

1. Brothel Prostitute

This mode of prostitution is a practice of prostitution in which customers come to brothels. The prostitute is managed by the pimp of the brothel owner, so that the income is partly for the pimp, they only receive 40% or maybe even less if the pimp finances the life of the prostitute in his house.

2. Call-girl Prostitute

Namely prostitutes who are usually invited or used to hotels, where the buyer lives, they are contacted through their intermediaries or by telephone. A portion of the produce is usually deducted a few percent of the yield by the waiter. Call-girls are categorized as semi-professionals.

2. Street or Public Prostitute

Namely prostitution where the prostitute looks for her clients on the streets or public places, then goes to a place they specify. Sometimes also in his client's vehicle.

3. Unorganized Professional Prostitute

A way in which the prostitute operates in a rented place, has a guard, where the taxi driver acts as a special intermediary. <http://www.keslusi.com/2009/04/prostitution.html>)

From those above explanation, prostitution is carried out openly and secretly. In the first category, prostitutes can be included in a narrow sense, who carry out prostitution either as a permanent or casual job.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In line with the problems and objectives of the study, the researchers used a qualitative research approach with the type of descriptive research. The type of data collected in this study can be divided into two namely secondary data and primary data. Source of data in this study focuses on human sources, events and documentation. In this study the sampling technique used was purposive sampling. The main data collection techniques in this study are interviews, observation and documentation. The analysis technique used in this study is to use interactive model analysis. According to Miles, Huberman and Saldana (2014: 14).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Implementation of Prostitution Prevention and Controlling Policy in Surabaya

One of the bases for closing localization as stated by Minister Khofifah in early March 2016 is the practice of human trafficking (Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 21 Year of 2007 concerning the Eradication of the Crime of Trafficking in Persons) which can be subject to criminal prosecution. He also believes that sexual exploitation and violence occurs on location, in addition to the abuse of drugs, alcohol and gambling. "These are all community diseases. If we want to build a prosperous, healthy and physically healthy community life, then localization must be closed," said Khofifah.

In Indonesia, prostitutes and prostitution service users cannot be subject to a single article in the Criminal Code (KUHP). According to the Legal Online page, the provisions of the Criminal Code can only be used to insure prostitution service providers or pimps based on the provisions of Article 296 jo. Article 506 of the Criminal Code. Efforts to dissolve the location of restrictions on prostitution and prostitution transactions are in line with the target set by the Ministry of Social Affairs in March 2016. "The central government continues to work with local governments to close localization, and it is targeted that in 2019 Indonesia must be free of localization," he said as quoted by Antara news agency. Based on government data published by Antara, the number of prostitution brothels in Indonesia previously reached 168 points. However, following the completion of 69 places, the remaining 99. East Java had the most localization sites with 41 points. However, since the end of 2015, 40 of them have closed. One is scattered in Balung Cangkring, Mojokerto. (<https://beritagar.id/artikel/berita/rencana-penutupan-lokalisasi-pelacuran-usung-ancaman-baru>)

Talks about prostitution and prostitution can be found in various media that provide a real picture of people's life, especially about prostitution or prostitution with all its problems. Prostitution activity is considered an economic commodity (even though it is prohibited by law) that can generate rupiah value or material for the perpetrator and the environment.

Regionally, the normative basis is the Governor of East Java Decree No: 188/617 / KPTS / 013/2010 concerning the Provincial Action Plan for the Eradication of Criminal Trafficking in Persons (TPPO) and Child Sexual Exploitation (ESA) in East Java Province 2010-2015. This is because based on a rapid study conducted by the ILO-IPEC in 2007, it estimated that the number of commercial sex workers under 18 years of age was around 1,244 children in Jakarta, Bandung 2,511, Yogyakarta 520, Surabaya 4,990, and Semarang 1,623. However, this number can be several times larger given the large number of commercial sex workers working in hidden, illegal and unregistered places (Topix news, 2008).

The phenomenon of prostitution is a portrait of activities that involve many parties in one relationship, such as pimps, brokers, as well as consumers or customers who are commonly referred to as male masher. Prostitution is rampant in the cities, the city conjures its residents to become "urban" against foreigners. Modernity in society creates a lifestyle that is currently the standard for the wider community. The commitment of the Surabaya Mayor to make Surabaya free of localization is evidenced by the closure of 4 localization area during 2012-2013, such as: 1. Localization of Dupak Bangunsari Moro Krembangan Sub-district, Krembangan District on December 21, 2012, 2. Localization of Kremil Tambak Asri, Morokrembangan Village, Krembangan District on May 28, 2013, 3. Klakahrejo Localization, Krembangan District on November 20, 2013, 4. Sememi Localization, Benowo sub-district on 23 December 2013. The details of the closed conditions of the localization were 61 guest houses, 50 pimps, and 163 prostitutes. The localization of Tambak Asri was 96

guest houses, 96 pimps, 354 prostitutes. Klakahrejo localizations are 70 guest houses, 65 pimps, 219 prostitutes and Sememi localizations, 32 guest houses, 22 people, 208 prostitutes.

3.2 Policy Implementation Problems

1. Technical difficulties

If you trace history, Dolly's presence is not just a legacy of history since the colonial era, but also holds many points of view, including socio-biological pathology, gender, sexuality market that leads to capitalization of prostitution, especially in economic issues. And the history of the sex industry in Surabaya is very unique. As the second largest city in Indonesia after Jakarta and as a trade route for East Indonesia, Surabaya during the Dutch colonialism developed as a leading port city, naval base, garrison base and as a final destination for railroad tracks. As a result of the development of this city, until 2014 Surabaya was still famous for its prostitution activities.

The success of a policy objective depends on technical requirements, including the ability to develop factors that guide work performance that is efficient both in terms of time and labor costs. It is hoped that the involvement of various parties will make it easier to achieve policy objectives. In preventing and overcoming prostitution, coordination is needed at every level of government, thereby facilitating the prevention and overcoming indicators of prostitution that need to be known together, including the most important indicator in the process of closing Dolly's localization is the human element where Dolly's closure concerns the interests of various human elements who have already rooted in panning for coffers of money through prostitution activities. Therefore, the toughest challenge for the Surabaya city government in implementing the Dolly localization closure policy is that many elements of the community contravene the plan to close Dolly's localization.

This can be seen in (merdeka.com June 16th 2014, 00:40 WIB) "Locals of localization. thousands of Commercial Sex Workers (CSW), pimps and street vendors Dolly held a free forum and open dialogue with National Commission of Human Rights. They regretted the city government policy that would close Dolly without coordination and did not care about their fate. Protests against Dolly's closure also came from 30 thousand workers throughout East Java on International Labor Day aka May Day, May 1st 2014. Among the workers is the Localization Workers Association (PPL). "We have never felt invited to talk by the government. The government has built public opinion as if the government training program is running smoothly, even though those who are included in the training are PKK (program at village level to educate women on various aspects of family welfare) women not sex workers (commercial sex workers)," said PPL coordinator Guntur. (30) in front of Grahadi State Building, Surabaya, East Java Province. Apeng, other PPL members also spoke up.

2. Diversity of Target Group Behavior

The more various behaviors are regulated, the more various services are provided, so that the more difficult it is to make firm and clear regulations. As a result, the greater the freedom of action that must be given to policy implementers in the community, thus the more diverse the behavior of the target group, the more implementers must be involved and of course, the greater the need for funds. Prostitution occurs because of deviant behavior in the form of free sex without regard to religious and social rules that apply in the community concerned. In Dolly, free sex occurs because in the context of activities to meet the economic needs of various parties involved in behavioral activities related to prostitution, including prostitutes themselves, owners of places where prostitution, tenants of prostitution places, pimps, traders in the prostitution environment, service services in a place of prostitution such as (transportation services, laundry services, banking services or banking ATMs). Therefore, the actual behavior that is the government's obligation to change is deviant public behavior, namely free sex behavior in Dolly to normal sexual behavior according to the religious order and the Indonesian nation's moral order which we know as behavioral change by having sex. in a wedding package.

Therefore, it is the government's duty to straighten out the sexual behavior of the Dolly community so they do not engage in deviant sexual behavior or provide centers for deviant sex activities as prostitution activities. It is not easy to change individual behavior, let alone group behavior, to change deviant sexual relations as a prostitution activity, because many people have an interest in and benefit from prostitution from an economic perspective.

3. Percentage of Target Group compared to Total Population

The spread of prostitution, especially localized, is often identified as free sex with an indication seen from the large number of sex workers localized. In Surabaya, there are quite a lot of sex sellers who are scattered in several brothels before being shut down by the government, including the number of prostitutes, pimps and the largest guest houses are in Dolly and Jarak areas. It is known that the number of CSWs in Dolly area is uncertain, it is known that most of the CSWs in the area are not residents of Surabaya City. Therefore, various efforts were made so that the number of sex workers did not increase. Even the City Government and Provincial Government continue to try to repatriate the prostitutes to their areas of origin. Based on data from the Surabaya City Social Service several days before the closure was carried out, the number of sex workers was 1,449 with around 311 pimps. This number has indeed increased from the data at the end of 2013 which was only 1,181 people, in 2012 there were 1,022 sex workers and 292 pimps. This amount is proposed for obtaining an allowance from the Ministry of Social Affairs. This is related to Dolly's plan to close on June 18th 2014.

The number of sex workers in the Dolly area had reached 5,000. This is what makes Dolly be very famous. In fact, many say that they haven't been to Surabaya if they have not been to Dolly. In addition, Dolly will usually

get new sex workers after the Eid holiday. Because usually the old prostitutes will bring people from their village to work in Dolly. This is also the reason why Dolly was closed before the fast. And the addition of prostitutes has also made the City Government even more assertive in carrying out closings, even though rejection continues. Most of Dolly's sex workers and pimps admitted that they did not agree with the closure plan. The reason is because the sex business that is being run is already prosperous. Tens of millions of rupiah can be obtained every month from one guesthouse.

(<https://regional.kompas.com/read/2014/06/18/0829077/Pasang.Surut.Jotal.PSK.Dolly>)

Furthermore, in okezone.com (Thursday June 19th 2014 15:09 WIB it was explained that the Surabaya City Government gave compensation of Rp. 5 million for each pimp and Rp. 5,050,000 for commercial sex workers. The funds were obtained by the Surabaya City Government from the East Java Provincial Government (for pimps). and the Ministry of Social Affairs (for prostitutes). "The total funds for prostitutes and pimps are IDR 7.317 billion from the Ministry of Social Affairs and IDR 1.555 billion from the East Java Provincial Government," said the Mayor of Surabaya, Tri Rismaharini in Surabaya, Thursday (19/6/2014). The requirement to withdraw the compensation fund is that pimps or prostitutes must show their identity cards. After that, the officers will match their identities with existing data. For prostitutes, compensation is given in the form of savings while pimps are cash. Risma hopes, the prostitutes and the pimps used the compensation money for Dolly's post-closure venture capital.

From the results of the research findings, it can be concluded that the percentage of target groups in the implementation of policies on prevention and overcoming prostitution, the number of commercial sex workers and the number of pimps is smaller than the number of residents in Putat Jaya which want Dolly's closure, and are supported by large funds for compensation for prostitutes and pimps and funds. Transfer of function of the guesthouse to SME center for affected residents. However, the majority of sex workers and pimps do not want to take compensation funds so that it is very potential for them with all their power and efforts to continue their profession through hidden prostitution and online prostitution as well as migration to carry out prostitution activities outside Dolly Jarak. This conditions still allow prostitutes to resume their profession at any time in Dolly Jarak, Surabaya area to serve customers who do not want to get prostitution outside the area, usually these commercial sex workers are known as recurrent sex workers.

Based on the results of research in the field, the Surabaya City Government in implementing policies on the prevention and handling of prostitution has succeeded in realizing the policy that has been announced in the form of closing Dolly's localization on June 18th, 2014 based on Regional Regulation Number 7 Year of 1999 issued by the Municipal Government of Surabaya Level II. On May 11th, 1999 which is a regulation regarding the prohibition of using buildings or places for immoral acts and enticements to commit immoral acts in Surabaya. With the closure of Dolly, it is hoped that the Surabaya City Government can transfer the function of guest houses as places for prostitution activities by purchasing these guest houses by the Surabaya City Government to become SME industrial centers and a change of profession for commercial sex workers, pimps and The affected communities in Dolly, where those whose economies used to depend on prostitution activities are expected to turn into the right breadwinners in accordance with the general religious and social order in Indonesian society. worship guidance) and MSME skills coaching or training is carried out for commercial sex workers and affected communities both before and after Dolly's closure.

But it cannot be denied that the implementation of policies on the prevention and prostitution control in Surabaya carried out by the Surabaya City Government can run smoothly but also experiences several obstacles, which are basically some groups of society who refuse to close Dolly's brothel, they consist of commercial sex workers, pimps. and the affected community by arguing that the point is that they still have an interest in the problem of rupiah panning through prostitution activities in Dolly's brothel. Their refusal was manifested in the form of demonstrations taking to the streets of long march carrying banners rejecting Dolly's closure and prostitution activities were still being carried out in several places in people's homes and carrying out prostitution transactions in cafes, in stalls, on the streets through brokers scattered where - which is all the way Dolly. From this explanation, it illustrates that the Surabaya City Government in implementing policies on the prevention and controlling of prostitution in the City of Surabaya is not optimal so the professional transfer expected by the Surabaya City Government is also less than optimal.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that the implementation of policies on the prevention and control of prostitution in Surabaya is not sufficient, if it is analyzed through a policy implementation model formulated based on the implementation model of Sabatier & Mazmanian (1983), but also needs to pay attention to Policy Instruments, including the voluntary mixed instrument model and the compulsory Howlett & Ramesh (1995) as well as actor collaboration in policy implementation, which consists of local, regional and national actors (Innes & Booher (2008) Howlett & Ramesh (1995)). Furthermore, several detailed conclusions are presented on the implementation of the Prostitution Prevention and Control Policy in Surabaya, which are described as follows:

1. The implementation of policies on the prevention and control of prostitution in Surabaya, it is known that the difficulty in closing Dolly's localization is due to the number of CSWs in the thousands, including the concern that more than thousands of families including children will lose their right to enjoy education and welfare, because the local community has so far depended on Dolly's localization. Loss of their livelihoods so that it will have an impact on unemployment and poverty and can expand social problems. The rejection of Dolly's localization closing was marked by a demonstration. Many elements of the community reject the

plan to close Dolly's brothel and the thousands of commercial sex workers in Dolly Jarak who will be rehabilitated and returned to their hometowns with a compensation for providing funds for a very large amount of business capital.

2. Based on the selected public policy instruments in the implementation of policies on the prevention and eradication of prostitution in Surabaya, it is known that from the voluntary model instrument, commercial sex workers (CSWs) have been given regular skills training as well as spiritual cleansing or recitation to be sent home by them. Surabaya City Government to return to their home areas and hand them over to their respective families just before the closing of Dolly Jarak, with compensation. However, not all prostitutes and pimps want to be given compensation on the grounds that the prostitutes and pimps who are given the compensation must fill out a statement that they are no longer allowed to work as sex workers in the city of Surabaya. Based on mixed instruments, the closure of the localization begins with socialization involving all levels of Surabaya City Government, all associations in Dolly, local neighbourhood / hamlet, community leaders, religious leaders, and officials. Subsequently, the Municipal Police installed a warning board which stated that the threat to those who were desperate to stage prostitution was installed by the Municipal Police, but the installation of a bulletin board at the end of Panjang street or near Dukuh Kupang encountered resistance. Dolly Residents and Jarak burned the noticeboard after previously hundreds of residents burned tires in the middle of the road as an act of resistance. Residents also attacked the police with stones throwing them. Another problem regarding compensation, many pimps who at the same time become hamlet's enter the names of other people either from prostitutes or not in the data collection of CSWs who will be submitted to the city government for compensation funds in the hope that if the compensation funds have been disbursed it will be shared between the pimps and Outside sex workers or ordinary women. Based on the mandatory instrument, the Surabaya City Government to carry out the prevention and control of prostitution in Dolly Jarak provides facilities to former pimps, women of hope for the future (former prostitutes) and affected communities, including: The government buys a former localization guesthouse in Dolly Jarak which is used for center activities. production centers, playgrounds, creative houses, mini futsal and so on; established several SME (Small and Medium Enterprise) and carried out the Dolly Saiki Fest 2017 Surabaya activities.

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